

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center

Milestone 1 Target Enabling Package

NIMA-related kinase 7 (NEK7)

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Corresponding Author	Pathum M Weerawarna
Contributing Authors	Jiahui Liu, Nidhi Walia, Emily Mason
Supervision	Kun Huang, Andrew Mesecar, Jeff Dage, Brent Clayton, Bruce Lamb, Alan Palkowitz, Timothy I. Richardson
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Affiliations	Indiana University School of Medicine, Indiana Biosciences Research Institute, Purdue University
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1. ABSTRACT

The TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) centers were created to support the validation and enablement of promising new drug targets for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease (AD) by providing high-quality research tools and capabilities. The centers share data, methods, and computational and experimental tools openly with the wider research community to aid in drug discovery and deepen the understanding of the complex biology of AD. These resources are

compiled into Target Enabling Packages (TEPs) that are made available through the Synapse AD Knowledge Portal.

Here, the IUSM Purdue TREAT-AD Center presents a TEP focused on NEK7 (NIMA-related kinase 7), a critical regulator of NLRP3 inflammasome activation that links cellular stress responses to innate immune signaling. We summarize the biological rationale for targeting NEK7 in AD, review the catalytic and scaffolding functions of NEK7 together with the structural features that govern each, and outline the experimental assays available for evaluating NEK7 engagement and downstream inflammasome activity. Experimental assays for evaluating NEK7 engagement and downstream inflammasome activity are discussed, together with emerging therapeutic modalities reported to target NEK7, including RNAi silencing approaches, targeted protein degradation strategies, and small molecules that disrupt the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. In addition, we provide practical recommendations on the selection of experimental assays and NEK7-targeting modalities that may be most suitable for investigating NEK7 biology and therapeutic potential in AD-related research.

2. INTRODUCTION

The NIMA-related kinase (NEK) family comprises a group of serine/threonine kinases that play important roles in the regulation of cell cycle progression, mitosis, and centrosome dynamics¹. In mammals, this family consists of 11 members (NEK1-NEK11) that share sequence similarity with the fungal mitotic regulator NIMA (Never In Mitosis kinase A)¹. Among these kinases, NEK7 is the smallest member of the family (~34.5 kDa human NEK7) and consists primarily of a catalytic kinase domain with only a short N-terminal extension^{2,3}. NEK7 is widely expressed in mammalian tissues and participates in multiple cellular processes, most notably mitotic progression and regulation of microtubule organization^{4,5}. Although initially characterized as a mitotic regulator, NEK7 was later discovered to play a critical role in innate immune signaling through its essential function in the NLRP3 inflammasome⁶, a multiprotein complex responsible for activating caspase-1 and promoting the maturation and secretion of the pro-inflammatory cytokines interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and interleukin-18 (IL-18). Mechanistic studies have demonstrated that NEK7 directly interacts with the leucine-rich repeat (LRR) domain of NLRP3 and is required for inflammasome assembly downstream of potassium efflux and other cellular stress signals⁶⁻⁸. This finding established NEK7 as a key regulatory factor linking cellular stress responses to NLRP3 inflammatory signaling pathways.

Importantly, dysregulation of NLRP3 inflammasome signaling has been strongly implicated in the pathogenesis of several chronic inflammatory disorders, including neurodegenerative diseases⁹. In the context of Alzheimer's disease (AD), persistent activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome in microglia has been shown to promote neuroinflammation, impair the clearance of amyloid β aggregates, and contribute to progressive neuronal damage in APP/PS1 mice¹⁰. Consistent with these observations, deletion of NLRP3 or caspase-1 in the same model enhances microglial A β phagocytosis and reduces amyloid deposition, demonstrating that inflammasome activation contributes to disease progression. Mechanistic studies have further shown that A β aggregates can directly activate the NLRP3 inflammasome in microglia, leading to caspase-1 activation and the maturation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β and IL-18¹¹. In addition, analyses of patient samples have revealed elevated expression of NLRP3 inflammasome

components and associated cytokines, including IL-1 β and IL-18, in peripheral immune cells and brain tissue from AD patients, suggesting enhanced inflammasome activation during disease progression^{12, 13}. Given that NEK7 is required for NLRP3 inflammasome activation, the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction has emerged as a critical molecular node in neuroinflammatory signaling associated with AD. Consequently, NEK7 has recently gained increasing attention as a potential therapeutic target for modulating NLRP3 inflammasome activation and associated neuroinflammatory processes in AD.

Motivated by this emerging therapeutic opportunity, we this Milestone 1 Target Enabling Package (M1 TEP) with the objective of summarizing and critically examining the current literature surrounding NEK7 and its biological validation and trackability as a potential drug target. Specifically, we discuss the biological rationale for targeting NEK7 in AD based on available experimental evidence and bioinformatic analyses, followed by an overview of its biological functions and the structural features that govern these functions. In addition, we summarize the available biochemical and cellular assays and discuss emerging chemical modalities that may enable the modulation of NEK7-licensed NLRP3 inflammasome activation and its quantitative evaluation. Where appropriate, we also provide recommendations on the selection of experimental assays and NEK7-targeting modalities that may be most suitable for investigating NEK7 biology and therapeutic potential in AD-related research.

3. BIOLOGICAL RATIONALE FOR TARGETING NEK7 IN AD

NEK7 is ubiquitously expressed across human tissues, with relatively high expression in the heart (RPKM ~38.5) and adipose tissue (~31.8), where RPKM (Reads Per Kilobase of transcript per Million mapped reads) reflects normalized gene expression levels that account for both sequencing depth and gene length, and displays similarly broad expression patterns in mice, including in the bladder, heart, and over two dozen other tissues¹⁴.

Figure 1. RNA expression of NEK7 in multiple tissues. Expression is quantified as nTPM (normalized Transcripts Per Million), which represents transcript abundance normalized for gene length and sequencing depth, enabling comparison across tissues.

Analysis of tissue-specific expression data from the Human Protein Atlas (HPA)¹⁵ and the Genotype-Tissue Expression (GTEx) project¹⁶ confirms that NEK7 is broadly expressed across multiple human organs, with notably high levels in the brain and adipose tissue (**Figure 1**). Within the brain, NEK7 transcripts are distributed across various regions with low regional specificity. The highest expression is observed in the spinal cord, followed by the midbrain and amygdala areas associated with motor control, emotional regulation, and stress response. Moderate expression in the hippocampal formation and hypothalamus suggests additional roles in memory processing, learning, and neuroendocrine function (**Figure 1**).

Figure 2. NEK7 RNA expression across AD-relevant brain regions from Agora (log₂CPM). ACC: Anterior Cingulate Cortex. CBE: Cerebellum. DLPFC: Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex. FP: Frontal Pole. IFG: Inferior Frontal Gyrus. PCC: Posterior Cingulate Cortex. PHG: Parahippocampal Gyrus. STG: Superior Temporal Gyrus. TCX: Temporal Cortex.

Agora is an interactive web application within the AD Knowledge Portal that integrates high-dimensional human transcriptomic, proteomic, and metabolomic datasets to systematically assess gene-level associations with AD¹⁷. Analysis of human brain RNA-seq data using Agora further supports the broad expression of NEK7 across multiple brain regions. All expression levels were reported as counts per million (CPM), with values exceeding the commonly accepted threshold for meaningful expression (CPM > 5; log₂CPM > ~2.3), indicating robust and widespread NEK7 transcription in the human brain (**Figure 2**).

Figure 3. Single-cell RNA expression level in multiple cell types for NEK7.

Single-cell RNA-seq data from the Human Protein Atlas (HPA) were analyzed to characterize the cell-type-specific expression patterns of NEK7 across diverse tissues and cell populations (**Figure 3**). NEK7 expression is notably enriched in glial cells, including astrocytes, microglia, oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPCs), and mature oligodendrocytes. This glial-predominant expression pattern supports proposed roles for NEK7 in neuroinflammatory signaling, glial proliferation, and the maintenance of central nervous system homeostasis.

Tissue	Subclass	Subtype	log2FC	AUROC	P value
Fresh	ADAM	GPNMB	0.583	0.560	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	AIF1	-0.847	0.412	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	CCL3	-0.825	0.414	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	HIF1A	0.530	0.555	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	HIST	0.057	0.506	0.003
Fresh	Adaptive	IFI44L	0.167	0.517	<0.001
Fresh	Adaptive	TMEM163	-0.660	0.431	<0.001
Fresh	Homeostatic	FRMD4A	0.420	0.544	<0.001
Fresh	Homeostatic	PICALM	0.499	0.552	<0.001
Fresh	PVM	CD163	0.363	0.538	<0.001
Fresh	exAM	ERN1	-0.177	0.482	<0.001
Frozen	ADAM	GPNMB	0.235	0.520	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	AIF1	-0.903	0.420	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	CCL3	-0.778	0.418	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	HIST	-0.152	0.487	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	HSPA1A	-0.363	0.467	<0.001
Frozen	Adaptive	TMEM163	-0.882	0.410	<0.001
Frozen	Homeostatic	FRMD4A	0.054	0.506	<0.001

Frozen	Homeostatic	PICALM	0.044	0.505	<0.001
Frozen	PVM	CD163	0.287	0.525	<0.001
Frozen	exAM	ERN1	-0.861	0.430	<0.001

Table 1. Differential expression analysis of NEK7 in single-nucleus RNA sequencing for several microglial subtypes. GPNMB microglia were significantly increased in both fresh and frozen samples from AD patients. AUROC, area under the receiver operating characteristic curve.

To investigate the transcriptional regulation of antioxidant pathways in human microglia within the context of AD, we analyzed a recently published single-nucleus RNA-sequencing dataset that defined 13 transcriptionally distinct microglial subtypes in both fresh and frozen brain tissue¹⁸. This analysis revealed statistically significant variation in NEK7 expression across specific microglial subtypes, as summarized in **Table 1**. NEK7 was expressed in multiple subtypes under both tissue conditions, with distinct expression patterns reflecting the functional heterogeneity of microglia in AD. These findings suggest that NEK7 may contribute to subtype-specific microglial responses during disease progression.

In fresh brain tissue, NEK7 expression was modestly upregulated in AD-associated microglia (ADAM), characterized by GPNMB expression, suggesting a potential link to AD-related microglial activity. Moderate upregulation was also observed in homeostatic microglia, marked by FRMD4A and PICALM, implicating NEK7 in the maintenance of baseline microglial function. In contrast, significant downregulation was noted in adaptive microglia, identified by markers such as AIF1, CCL3, and TMEM163, indicating reduced NEK7 expression in inflammation-responsive states. HIF1A-defined populations exhibited modest upregulation, suggesting marker-level heterogeneity in NEK7 regulation across adaptive microglial states. *Ex vivo* activated microglia (exAM), marked by ERN1, also showed slight downregulation, supporting a role for NEK7 in the modulation of inflammatory responses. In frozen tissue samples, expression patterns were generally consistent but attenuated. NEK7 remained slightly upregulated in ADAM and perivascular macrophages (PVM), marked by CD163, highlighting a potential role in perivascular immune regulation. Conversely, pronounced downregulation persisted in adaptive microglial subtypes, including those marked by AIF1, CCL3, TMEM163, HIST, and HSPA1A, indicating consistent suppression of NEK7 in stress-responsive microglial populations across tissue preservation methods. Additionally, at least two NEK7 isoforms have been reported in humans via alternative splicing, according to UniProt (Q8TDX7)¹⁹. However, their structural and functional distinctions remain largely uncharacterized. Furthermore, no well-established disease-associated mutations or variants have been documented in current genomic databases, suggesting that functional characterization of NEK7 isoforms along with a search for disease-associated variants are promising areas for future investigations.

Figure 4. Functional interaction network analysis using NEK7. Red circle: Central gene, Blue triangle: Regulated by, Green square: Regulates, Yellow diamond: Binds, Solid line: Regulates, Long-dash: Regulated by, Short-dash: Binds.

We constructed a functional interaction network to investigate the biological roles and regulatory relationships of NEK7 using Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA[®], QIAGEN), revealing a complex landscape of molecular interactions (**Figure 4**). NEK7 functions as a central hub, engaging directly with several protein partners through binding interactions, including kinases (NEK6, NEK8, NEK9), inflammasome components (NLRP3), and signaling intermediates (DDX1, EML4, ANKS6). Notably, NEK7 is regulated by a range of inflammatory and metabolic stimuli, such as lipopolysaccharide (LPS), A20 (TNFAIP3), and adenosine triphosphate (ATP), underscoring its role in inflammation-mediated signaling pathways. In turn, NEK7 influences key immune effectors, including IL-1 β , CASP1, and IL12A, reinforcing its involvement in inflammasome activation and immune regulation. Collectively, these interactions position NEK7 as a critical molecular node linking inflammasome signaling, cellular metabolism, and immune pathways, with potential relevance to AD pathophysiology.

Finally, Gene Ontology (GO) enrichment analysis highlights the potential involvement of NEK7 in AD through several key functional categories based on IPA[®] (QIAGEN). Under Molecular Function (MF), NEK7 exhibits protein serine/threonine kinase activity, which is critical for phosphorylation-mediated signaling. Aberrant kinase activity, including that of NEK7, has been implicated in the pathological phosphorylation of tau, contributing to neurofibrillary tangle formation and disrupted intracellular signaling in AD neurons.

Additionally, NEK7 displays ATP binding capacity, a requirement for its kinase function, thereby linking it to energy-dependent signaling pathways that are often impaired in AD due to mitochondrial dysfunction and metabolic deficits. In the category of Biological Process (BP), NEK7 plays a central role in the positive regulation of NLRP3 inflammasome complex assembly, a key mechanism of innate immune activation. By promoting NLRP3 inflammasome formation, NEK7 contributes to chronic neuroinflammation, a hallmark of AD progression. NEK7 is also involved in the regulation of the mitotic cell cycle, a process typically inactive in post-mitotic neurons. However, aberrant cell cycle re-entry has been observed in AD and is associated with neuronal apoptosis, further implicating NEK7 in neurodegenerative processes. For Cellular Component (CC), NEK7 is associated with the microtubule cytoskeleton, suggesting a role in maintaining cytoskeletal integrity. Given that microtubule destabilization is a hallmark of tau-related pathology in AD, NEK7's interaction with microtubules may contribute to structural dysfunction. Moreover, its localization to the spindle pole during cell division implicates it in mitotic spindle organization, an observation particularly relevant to AD, where dysregulation of cell cycle machinery occurs in vulnerable neuronal populations.

4. BIOLOGICAL FUNCTION OF NEK7

NEK7 has two main distinct functions, namely, catalytic and scaffolding (**Figure 5**), that are crucial for its roles in cell division and NLRP3 inflammasome activation, which are important for normal cellular processes and stress responses in organisms and have been extensively reviewed in the literature^{20, 21}. A brief overview of these two major functions is provided below.

Figure 5. Dual functional roles of NEK7 in mitotic regulation and NLRP3 inflammasome activation. (A) Catalytic role of NEK7 in mitosis. NEK7 is activated downstream of CDK1 and Plk1 through phosphorylation-dependent activation of NEK9. Activated NEK7 phosphorylates mitotic substrates such as RGS2, EML4, and Eg5 (KIF11), regulating spindle organization, microtubule remodeling, and centrosome separation during M-phase progression. Because NEK7 participates in mitotic signaling during the M phase, its availability for inflammasome signaling is largely restricted to the interphase. **(B) Kinase-independent scaffolding role of NEK7 in NLRP3 inflammasome activation.** NLRP3 activation proceeds through a two-step process consisting of priming and activation. During priming, pattern recognition receptor signaling (e.g., TNFR, TLR, and IL-1R pathways) activates NF-κB dependent transcription, increasing the expression of NLRP3 and pro-inflammatory cytokine precursors. Subsequent cellular stress signals, including ion fluxes such as K⁺ efflux, promote NLRP3 oligomerization. NEK7 binds NLRP3 and acts as a structural scaffold that stabilizes inflammasome assembly and facilitates the recruitment of ASC and pro-caspase-1. Activated caspase-1 cleaves pro-IL-1β and pro-IL-18 and processes gasdermin D (GSDMD), whose N-terminal fragment forms membrane pores that enable cytokine release and pyroptotic cell death.

4.1 NEK7 Catalytic Function and the Regulation of Mitosis

The catalytic activity of NEK7 plays a central role in mitotic progression by regulating centrosome function, microtubule nucleation, and mitotic spindle assembly^{4, 5, 22, 23}. During the cell cycle, NEK7 localizes

predominantly to the centrosome⁴ and transiently to additional mitotic structures, including spindle poles and the midbody²⁴, suggesting a direct role in coordinating centrosome dynamics and spindle organization during cell division. Activation of NEK7 occurs within a hierarchical mitotic kinase cascade involving NEK9 and other upstream regulators (**Figure 5A**). In this pathway, phosphorylation of NEK9 by cyclin-dependent kinase 1 (CDK1) and Polo-like kinase 1 (Plk1) promotes the activation of the NEK9–NEK6/NEK7 signaling module, which subsequently regulates proteins involved in centrosome separation and spindle assembly²⁵. Structural studies have further shown that interaction with NEK9 relieves autoinhibition within the NEK7 kinase domain²⁶, enabling catalytic activation and downstream signaling during mitosis (the structural basis for this NEK9-mediated NEK7 activation will be discussed below). NEK7 activity within this cascade contributes to the phosphorylation of mitotic regulators, such as the kinesin motor protein Eg5/KIF11²⁵, thereby facilitating centrosome separation during prophase and ensuring proper spindle bipolarity. Additional substrates and interacting partners further support the role of NEK7 as a key catalytic regulator of spindle organization. For example, NEK7 phosphorylates the regulator of G protein signaling protein RGS2, promoting its localization to the mitotic spindle, where it contributes to proper spindle organization and orientation²⁷. Similarly, phosphorylation of the microtubule-associated protein EML4 by NEK6 and NEK7 promotes its dissociation from microtubules during mitosis, facilitating efficient chromosome congression at the metaphase plate²⁸.

Functional studies have demonstrated that depletion or loss of NEK7 results in pronounced mitotic abnormalities, including monopolar and multipolar spindle formation, impaired microtubule nucleation, and arrest at multiple stages of mitosis, indicating that NEK7 catalytic activity is required for proper mitotic progression⁴. Mechanistically, NEK7 contributes to centrosome maturation and microtubule organization by regulating the accumulation of pericentriolar material and γ -tubulin-dependent microtubule nucleation. Cells lacking NEK7 exhibit reduced centrosomal γ -tubulin levels and diminished microtubule nucleation activity, leading to defects in spindle assembly and chromosome segregation⁴. In addition to its role in centrosomal microtubule nucleation, studies have demonstrated that NEK7 also regulates microtubule dynamic instability by controlling microtubule growth and catastrophe dynamics, further supporting a role for NEK7 in maintaining proper spindle microtubule behavior during mitosis²⁹. These findings collectively demonstrate that NEK7 catalytic activity regulates mitotic progression by coordinating centrosome maturation, microtubule dynamics, and spindle assembly, thereby ensuring accurate chromosome segregation and proper completion of cell division.

The potential involvement of NEK7 in human diseases associated with dysregulated cell division has been extensively reviewed elsewhere²¹. Briefly, altered NEK7 expression or genetic perturbation has been reported in several malignancies, including hepatocellular carcinoma³⁰, gallbladder cancer³¹, and retinoblastoma³², suggesting that disruption of NEK7-dependent mitotic regulation may contribute to pathological cell proliferation. However, much of the available evidence derives from transcriptional or genetic studies that associate NEK7 with disease phenotypes but do not specifically distinguish the contribution of its catalytic mitotic activity. Consequently, it remains unclear whether the catalytic kinase function of NEK7 is the primary driver of these pathological processes.

4.2 NEK7 Scaffolding Function and the Regulation of NLRP3 Inflammasome Activation

In addition to its catalytic role in mitotic regulation, NEK7 performs a distinct kinase-independent scaffolding function that is essential for the activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome (**Figure 5B**). The NLRP3 inflammasome is a cytosolic multiprotein signaling complex that mediates innate immune responses by activating caspase-1 and promoting the maturation of the pro-inflammatory cytokines interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and interleukin-18 (IL-18)³³. Activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome generally requires two sequential signals. The first signal, commonly referred to as the priming step, is triggered by pathogen-associated or damage-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs or DAMPs) that activate pattern recognition receptors, such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs), tumor necrosis factor receptor (TNFR), or interleukin-1 receptor (IL-1R)³³. These signaling events activate NF- κ B-dependent transcriptional programs that increase the expression of inflammasome components, including NLRP3, pro-IL-1 β , and pro-IL-18.

Following priming, a second activation signal is triggered by diverse cellular stressors, including extracellular ATP, pore-forming toxins, crystalline particles, and viral RNA³³. These stimuli disrupt cellular homeostasis and induce ion fluxes, such as potassium efflux, calcium signaling, chloride efflux, mitochondrial dysfunction, and reactive oxygen species generation, which collectively promote the activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome. Under these conditions, NEK7 directly interacts with the LRR domain of NLRP3, an interaction that is now recognized as an essential step in inflammasome assembly³⁴. This interaction promotes the oligomerization of NLRP3 and the recruitment of the adaptor protein ASC, ultimately leading to caspase-1 activation and the proteolytic processing of pro-IL-1 β and pro-IL-18 into their mature inflammatory forms.

More recently, Xu *et al.* reported that NEK7 is phosphorylated by JNK1 at Thr190/Thr191 during NLRP3 activation downstream of K⁺ efflux and GSDMD and that this phosphorylation strengthens NEK7–NLRP3 binding³⁵. Functional studies using phosphorylation-deficient Nek7 T190V/T191V macrophages showed reduced inflammasome assembly, caspase-1 processing, and IL-1 β release, supporting a model in which NEK7 phosphorylation serves as a positive feedback event that amplifies canonical NLRP3 inflammasome activation³⁵. Interestingly, genetic and biochemical studies have revealed that NEK7 availability in cells is limited, creating a functional mutual exclusivity between mitosis and inflammasome activation, such that NEK7 cannot simultaneously participate in both processes⁸. This phenomenon arises because the C-terminal lobe of NEK7 interacts with NEK9 during mitosis to enable kinase activation^{25, 26}, whereas the same structural region is required for binding to the LRR domain of NLRP3 during inflammasome assembly³⁴. Consequently, when NEK7 is engaged in the NEK9–NEK7 mitotic complex, it cannot form the interactions with NLRP3 that are required for inflammasome activation. The structural basis for this competition will be discussed in detail later in this TEP. This observation highlights the dual, context-dependent biological functions of NEK7 as either a mitotic kinase or an inflammasome regulatory scaffold.

Although NEK7 is widely regarded as a central licensing factor for NLRP3 inflammasome assembly, recent studies suggest that alternative mechanisms of NLRP3 activation may exist under certain cellular contexts. In particular, Schmacke *et al.* reported that NLRP3 inflammasome formation can occur independently of NEK7 in human macrophages through an alternative priming mechanism mediated by IKK β ³⁶. In this study, IKK β activity promoted the recruitment of NLRP3 to phosphatidylinositol-4-phosphate (PI4P)-enriched membranes at the trans-Golgi network, thereby facilitating inflammasome assembly without requiring NEK7. These findings suggest that IKK β -dependent priming may substitute for NEK7 in certain human cell

systems. Importantly, this mechanism appears to be context-dependent, as numerous studies in murine macrophages have demonstrated a strict requirement for NEK7 in canonical NLRP3 inflammasome activation^{6, 8, 37}. Consequently, while these observations indicate that NEK7-independent pathways of NLRP3 activation may exist, NEK7 remains widely considered the predominant physiological regulator of inflammasome assembly.

Because aberrant activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome contributes to numerous inflammatory, metabolic, and cardiovascular disorders, such as atherosclerosis^{38, 39}, type 2 diabetes⁴⁰⁻⁴², gout⁴³, systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE)⁴⁴, inflammatory bowel disease (IBD)⁴⁵ including Crohn's disease^{46, 47}, the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction has emerged as an attractive therapeutic target. Importantly, NLRP3 inflammasome signaling pathway has emerged as a major driver of chronic neuroinflammation and is therefore considered one of the most relevant molecular mechanisms contributing to the progression of AD and other neurodegenerative disorders^{48, 49}. In particular, chronic activation of NLRP3 signaling in microglia is believed to promote sustained neuroinflammation and neuronal damage during the progression of AD. Consequently, pharmacological strategies that target NEK7 and disrupt NEK7–NLRP3 interactions or prevent inflammasome assembly represent promising approaches for modulating neuroinflammatory pathways implicated in neurodegeneration.

5. STRUCTURAL BIOLOGY OF NEK7

The dual catalytic and scaffolding functions of NEK7 are mediated by the distinct structural features of the protein, which have been extensively characterized using X-ray crystallography and cryo-EM. Unlike many kinases that possess additional regulatory or interaction domains beyond the catalytic core to mediate protein-protein interactions (PPIs), NEK7 comprises a single canonical kinase domain². Thus, both its enzymatic activity and scaffolding function arise from conformational and surface features embedded within the catalytic domain itself rather than from separate structural modules. From a drug targeting perspective, identifying and understanding the structural basis underlying these dual functions is essential for developing therapeutics that selectively target each function of NEK7, either through ATP-competitive inhibition of kinase activity or through disruption of PPIs that underlie its scaffolding function. Accordingly, the following sections provide a structural overview of NEK7 in the context of its catalytic kinase activity and scaffolding function in NLRP3 inflammasome assembly.

5.1 Catalytic Domain and Structural Basis of NEK7 Kinase Function

As mentioned above, unlike other NEK family members, such as NEK9, which possesses a central Regulator of Chromosome Condensation-1 (RCC1)-like domain and a C-terminal domain (CTD)¹, NEK7 is structurally minimal and consists almost exclusively of a bilobal catalytic kinase domain. Human NEK7 is a ~34.5 kDa protein consisting of an N-terminal disordered region (residues 1–21), an N-terminal extension (NTE motif; residues 22–32), and a catalytic kinase domain (residues 33–299). The NTE domain contributes to substrate recognition and consists primarily of β -strands and a regulatory α C-helix, similar to that of other protein kinases such as CDK2 (**Figure 6A**)³. The C-terminal lobe (C-lobe) is predominantly α -helical and contains catalytic and activation loop segments, the latter playing a key regulatory role in catalytic activation. Biochemical studies have shown that NEK7 exhibits low intrinsic kinase activity and undergoes

slow autophosphorylation-dependent activation²⁶. Phosphorylation of a conserved serine residue (Ser195 in human NEK7) within the activation loop significantly enhances the catalytic activity by stabilizing the active conformation²⁶. The ATP-binding site is located in the cleft between the two lobes, and catalytic activity requires precise positioning of the conserved β 3 lysine and α C glutamate to form a Lys63–Glu82 salt bridge that properly orients ATP for phosphoryl transfer. A distinctive feature of NEK7 is the presence of a DLG motif at the beginning of the activation loop, rather than the commonly found DFG motif in most kinases. Despite this substitution, the DLG motif fulfills an equivalent structural role in coordinating catalytic activity and contributes to the assembly of the regulatory hydrophobic spine.

Figure 6. Structural basis of NEK7 autoinhibition and activation by NEK9. (A) Crystal structure of apo NEK7 (PDB ID: 2WQM) showing the canonical bilobal kinase architecture composed of an N-terminal lobe and a predominantly α -helical C-terminal lobe. In the autoinhibited state, Tyr97 located on the β 4 strand adopts a “Tyr-down” conformation in which its aromatic side chain projects into the ATP-binding cleft and stabilizes an inactive state. This conformation sterically restricts the inward positioning of the α C-helix and disrupts the formation of the catalytically competent Lys63–Glu82 salt bridge. **(B)** Crystal structure of the NEK7^{Y97F}–NEK9⁸¹⁰⁻⁸¹⁸ complex (PDB ID: 5DE2 protomer B) showing NEK7 bound to a C-terminal peptide fragment of NEK9. Although a peptide spanning NEK9 residues 810 to 828 was used for crystallization, the view shown here corresponds to protomer B, in which the electron density was only modeled up to residue 818. In this protomer, Tyr97 was mutated to phenylalanine (Y97F), and Phe97 adopts a “Phe-up” conformation rotated away from the ATP-binding site, relieving autoinhibition. Binding of the NEK9 C-terminal region to a groove on the C-lobe promotes conformational rearrangement of regulatory elements, consistent with NEK9-mediated activation of NEK7. (The NTE motif is depicted in cyan, the α C-helix in amber, the DLG motif in light green, and the NEK9⁸¹⁰⁻⁸¹⁸ peptide in orange).

The first crystal structure of full-length NEK7 reported in the literature revealed an unexpected autoinhibited conformation, characterized by a unique regulatory tyrosine motif (**Figure 6A**)³. In this structure (PDB: 2WQM), Tyr97, located on the β 4 strand of the N-lobe, adopts a “Tyr-down” rotamer in which its aromatic side chain projects into the ATP-binding cleft. This conformation stabilizes an inactive state through multiple coordinated effects. The hydroxyl group of Tyr97 forms a hydrogen bond with the backbone amide of Leu180 within the DLG motif, thereby stabilizing an inactive activation loop. Simultaneously, the aromatic ring sterically prevents the inward positioning of the α C-helix, disrupting the formation of the essential Lys63–Glu82 salt bridge and misaligning the regulatory spine. Mutation of Tyr97 to alanine or phenylalanine significantly increases basal kinase activity, with the Y97A mutant exhibiting approximately a fivefold increase relative to the wild-type enzyme, confirming that Tyr97 functions as an intrinsic autoinhibitory element rather than merely contributing to structural packing.

Subsequent structural and biochemical studies conducted by the same research group using the NEK7^{Y97F} mutation demonstrated that NEK7 activation is promoted by interaction with the CTD of NEK9²⁶. In this work, residues 810-828 of NEK9 were identified as the minimal NEK7-binding region, and the crystal structure of the NEK7^{Y97F}-NEK9⁸¹⁰⁻⁸¹⁸ complex (PDB: 5DE2 protomer B) revealed that NEK9⁸¹⁰⁻⁸¹⁸ binds to a groove on the C-lobe of NEK7 (**Figure 6B**). Importantly, this interaction promotes back-to-back dimerization of NEK7, which was not observed in the original NEK7 WT structure and is mediated primarily through N-lobe interfaces, and is structurally coupled to conformational rearrangements surrounding residue 97 in one of the NEK7 protomers (chain B). In this protomer, Phe97 (Tyr97 in WT) adopts a “Phe-up” conformation, rotating away from the active site and thereby relieving NEK7 autoinhibition. In the other protomer (chain A), Phe97 adopts a “Phe-down” conformation similar to that observed in the NEK7 WT autoinhibited conformation. Consistent with this structural mechanism, biochemical kinase assays showed that the NEK9-CTD markedly increased the catalytic activity of NEK7 WT to levels comparable to those observed for the constitutively active Y97A mutant, supporting the relief of Tyr97-mediated autoinhibition through NEK9-induced dimerization. Overall, the proposed NEK9-CTD-promoted back-to-back dimerization of NEK7, which mediates the release of autoinhibition, represents a distinct regulatory strategy compared to the classical activation loop phosphorylation-dependent regulation observed in many kinases. From a drug targeting perspective, these structural insights define two potential conformational states of NEK7: an autoinhibited Tyr-down monomer and a dimerization-competent Tyr-up active state, which together provide a mechanistic framework for the rational design of inhibitors that selectively target the catalytic function of NEK7. In terms of ligand-bound X-ray crystal structures, only a few are available, including one structure bound to ADP (PDB: 2WQN) and two structures of WT NEK7 (PDB: 6S75) and the NEK7 SRS mutant (PDB: 6S73) bound to a NEK2 inhibitor, which exhibits weak reported binding to NEK7.

5.2 Structural Basis of NEK7 Scaffolding Function in NLRP3 Inflammasome Activation

Over the past several years, structural studies have progressively refined the mechanistic understanding of the scaffolding function of NEK7 in NLRP3 inflammasome activation. As shown in **Figure 7**, these studies have marked key milestones, beginning with the first structure of the inactive NLRP3 in complex with NEK7 C-lobe⁷, which established the scaffolding interface, followed by the identification of inactive closed-cage

NLRP3 oligomers⁵⁰ and the active NLRP3 inflammasome disc⁵¹. The most recent discovery of open NLRP3 oligomer intermediates³⁴ has helped establish a definitive structural role for NEK7 by demonstrating how NEK7 remodels NLRP3 oligomers to enable inflammasome assembly. A high-level description of these key milestones is provided below.

Figure 7. Timeline of cryo-EM structural milestones defining the scaffolding role of NEK7 in NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Cryo-EM studies progressively revealed the structural basis of NEK7-mediated NLRP3 activation, beginning with the first NEK7-NLRP3 complex structure (PDB ID: 6NPY, 2019), which established the direct scaffolding interface between the NEK7 C-lobe and the NACHT-LRR region of NLRP3. Subsequent structures identified the autoinhibited closed double-ring cage architecture of full-length NLRP3 (PDB ID: 7LFH, 2021-2022), defining the resting oligomeric state. Later studies resolved the active NLRP3 inflammasome disc (PDB ID: 8EJ4, 2022), revealing the oligomeric architecture competent for ASC recruitment and suggesting a remodeling role for NEK7. Most recently, cryo-EM structures captured an open cage intermediate (PDB ID: 8SWF, 2023-2024), demonstrating that NEK7 disrupts closed NLRP3 oligomers and stabilizes activation-competent monomeric and dimeric intermediates. Together, these structures establish a stepwise structural framework in which NEK7 remodels NLRP3 oligomers to license inflammasome assembly. (NACHT domain is colored in white, LRR domain is colored in cyan, and NEK7 is colored in yellow). **Note:** Closed and open NLRP3 cage structures are observed only in the absence of NEK7 and therefore do not contain NEK7. NEK7 is observed only with NLRP3 monomers, dimers, and the active inflammasome disc.

5.2.1 First cryo-EM Structure of the NEK7-NLRP3 Complex

The first structural insight into the scaffolding role of NEK7 in NLRP3 activation was provided by cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM) studies by Hao Wu in 2019, which resolved a complex between NEK7 and an N-terminal pyrin-domain-deleted form of NLRP3 (NLRP3_{ΔPYD}) (PDB ID: 6NPY)⁷. The resulting atomic model included nearly the entire NACHT-LRR core of NLRP3 and the C-lobe of NEK7, demonstrating that NEK7 engages NLRP3 primarily through its C-terminal kinase lobe. This interaction occurs across multiple surfaces spanning the NLRP3 NACHT and LRR domains and is mediated in part by electrostatic

complementarity between the positively charged NEK7 C-lobe and negatively charged regions of NLRP3. Notably, the NEK7 activation loop was disordered and did not directly participate in the interface, consistent with biochemical observations that both catalytically active and inactive NEK7 can support NLRP3 activation. Mutagenesis and biochemical binding experiments confirmed the functional importance of the observed interface. Although this study provided the first direct structural evidence for NEK7 binding to NLRP3 and established the structural basis of its scaffolding function, the oligomeric assembly of the NLRP3 inflammasome disc was inferred from homology modeling based on the NLRC4 oligomer structure, leaving the structural role of NEK7 in higher-order inflammasome assembly unresolved.

5.2.2 Closed Cage NLRP3 Oligomer Identified as the Autoinhibited State

Subsequent cryo-EM studies by the same research group resolved the structure of full-length mouse NLRP3 in the absence of NEK7 and revealed that, under basal conditions, NLRP3 assembles into a 12- to 16-subunit double-ring cage, primarily stabilized by LRR–LRR interactions, in which NLRP3 adopts a closed, inactive conformation (**Figure 7**; PDB ID: 7LFH)⁵⁰. Consistent with these findings, similar closed cage oligomeric structures of full-length NLRP3 were later independently observed by other research groups^{52, 53}, confirming this architecture as a conserved autoinhibited resting state associated with membranes and binding preferentially to acidic membrane lipids of the Golgi and mitochondria through positively charged NACHT surfaces. In this closed cage architecture, the pyrin domains are sequestered within the interior of the assembly, thereby preventing premature ASC recruitment and inflammasome activation. This oligomeric form is predominantly membrane-associated and represents a stimulus-responsive, pre-activation state of NLRP3. Structure-guided mutagenesis further demonstrated that disruption of the double-ring cage impairs inflammasome assembly, caspase-1 activation, and pyroptotic cell death, establishing the cage structure as a physiologically relevant intermediate for activation. Importantly, this and other studies that defined the inactive oligomeric architecture of NLRP3 provide a structural framework for understanding how subsequent NEK7 engagement and conformational remodeling enable inflammasome activation. However, they do not provide direct structural evidence of this process.

5.2.3 Cryo-EM Structure of the NEK7-Bound Active Inflammasome Disc

Building upon their earlier structural characterization of the inactive NLRP3 cage, the Hao Wu group next reported the first cryo-EM structure of the active NLRP3 inflammasome disc in complex with NEK7 and ASC, providing critical insight into the activated oligomeric architecture⁵¹. In this structure, NLRP3 assembles into a disc-shaped oligomer composed of multiple NACHT domains forming the central scaffold, with the LRR domains and NEK7 molecules positioned peripherally. Surprisingly, structural analysis revealed that neither NEK7 nor the LRR domains directly participate in the oligomerization interfaces that stabilize the inflammasome disc, indicating that their roles extend beyond simply forming structural contacts within the active assembly. Instead, based on a comparison with previously determined inactive cage structures, the authors proposed that the LRR domain stabilizes the autoinhibited cage, whereas interaction with the centrosome-resident protein NEK7 promotes the disruption of the inactive cage and facilitates conformational remodeling into the active inflammasome disc capable of recruiting ASC. However, this mechanism was primarily inferred from structural comparisons and cellular observations and direct structural evidence demonstrating how NEK7 mediates cage disassembly and promotes the

formation of activation-competent NLRP3 intermediates was only provided in their subsequent structural studies.

Figure 8. Current structure-based mechanism of NEK7-mediated NLRP3 inflammasome activation (A-E), opportunities for therapeutic intervention (1-3), and available assay platforms. During priming, elevated cellular levels of NLRP3 assemble into autoinhibited closed-cage oligomers stabilized by LRR–LRR interactions (A). ATP binding and hydrolysis within the NACHT domain promote conformational rearrangement and conversion of the closed cage into an open, activation-competent oligomeric state (B). NEK7 binds to the LRR domain of NLRP3 and disrupts oligomer-stabilizing interfaces, promoting dissociation of both closed and open cages into NEK7–NLRP3 monomeric and dimeric intermediates in dynamic equilibrium (C). These intermediates can undergo further conformational activation, including cooperative NACHT domain opening (“passive activation”), generating activation-competent NEK7–NLRP3 complexes (D). Subsequent uni- and bi-directional assembly with the adaptor protein ASC leads to the formation of the fully active NLRP3 inflammasome complex (E), resulting in caspase-1 activation, cytokine maturation (IL-1 β and IL-18), and pyroptosis. The figure also highlights experimental approaches used to interrogate these steps, including biochemical and biophysical assays to characterize NEK7–NLRP3

interactions and NEK7-small-molecule interactions, cellular inflammasome activation assays, and three main therapeutic intervention strategies targeting NEK7: **(1)** gene silencing, **(2)** targeted protein degradation, and **(3)** inhibition of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPIs. (NACHT domain is colored in white, LRR domain is colored in cyan, and NEK7 is colored in yellow)

5.2.4 Open Octamer Intermediate and Structural Establishment of NEK7-Mediated NLRP3 Inflammasome Activation

To address the unresolved intermediate steps linking the inactive cage to the active inflammasome assembly, the Hao Wu group subsequently performed comprehensive cryo-EM and biochemical analyses to directly capture activation intermediates of NLRP3³⁴. In this work, cryo-EM structures revealed that NLRP3_{ΔPYD} forms an open octamer characterized by an approximately 90° hinge rotation within the NACHT domain, representing a previously unobserved activation intermediate. Mutational disruption of interfaces specific to this open oligomer impaired IL-1β signaling, demonstrating its functional importance in inflammasome activation. Based on these new structural findings and extensive biochemical, mutational, and cellular functional studies, the authors proposed a comprehensive mechanism of NLRP3 inflammasome activation, which assigns a definitive role to NEK7 in this process (**Figure 8**). According to this mechanism, increased cellular levels of NLRP3 during the priming step primarily exist in a closed conformation that assembles into inactive cage-like oligomers stabilized by LRR–LRR interactions. Self-activation of NLRP3 within these closed oligomers occurs through ATP binding and hydrolysis, which induces a conformational change in the NACHT domain and converts the closed cage into an open, activation-competent oligomeric state. Both closed and open oligomeric assemblies are competent for trafficking along microtubules to the microtubule-organizing center (MTOC). NEK7 plays a critical role by binding to the LRR domain of NLRP3 and disrupting the LRR-mediated oligomer interfaces that stabilize both closed and open cage structures, thereby promoting oligomer dissociation into NEK7–NLRP3 monomers and dimers in dynamic equilibrium. In addition, closed NEK7–NLRP3 intermediates can undergo passive activation through cooperative conformational coupling with neighboring open NEK7–NLRP3 complexes, facilitating NACHT domain opening without requiring additional ATP hydrolysis. Ultimately, open NEK7–NLRP3 monomers and dimers undergo uni- and bidirectional assembly with ASC to form the fully active NLRP3 inflammasome complex. Collectively, this structurally and biochemically supported mechanism defines a central role for NEK7 in remodeling NLRP3 oligomers and licensing inflammasome activation, thereby revealing new opportunities for medicinal chemistry strategies aimed at disrupting NEK7–NLRP3 interactions to therapeutically suppress NLRP3 inflammasome activation.

5.3 Recommended Structural Biology Strategy for NEK7

For programs aimed at developing ATP-competitive or allosteric kinase inhibitors that engage the catalytic domain, X-ray crystallography remains the most informative strategy, supported by the existing apo (PDB: 2WQM), ADP-bound (PDB: 2WQN), and NEK9-CTD-activated (PDB: 5DE2) structures, which together capture both the autoinhibited- and activation-states of NEK7 and define the conformational landscape relevant for inhibitor design. Structures that capture the Tyr-down autoinhibited state and the Phe-up active state provide a basis for the rational design of inhibitors that selectively stabilize either conformation, including type II inhibitors that exploit the DLG-out pocket. Cryo-EM can be used to inform targeting strategies focused on the NEK7–NLRP3 scaffolding interaction. The NEK7–NLRP3_{ΔPYD} complex

(PDB: 6NPY) defines the binding interface, while the full-length closed cage (PDB: 7LFH) and open cage intermediate (PDB: 8SWF), which lack NEK7, delineate NLRP3 conformations that are incompatible with NEK7 engagement. The active inflammasome disc (PDB: 8EJ4) captures the functional assembly. Together, these structures define the conformational landscape governing NEK7 recruitment and provide a framework for interpreting how ligands modulate inflammasome assembly. To extend the impact of cryo-EM, complementary biophysical methods are recommended, such as hydrogen–deuterium exchange mass spectrometry (HDX-MS), to further define ligand-induced conformational changes and interface remodeling that cannot be resolved at the resolution of cryo-EM.

6. ASSAYS FOR EVALUATING NEK7-TARGETING MODALITIES IN NLRP3 INFLAMMASOME INHIBITION

Based on the current understanding of the mechanism of NEK7 involvement in NLRP3 inflammasome activation, the binding of NEK7 to NLRP3 oligomeric cages and disruption of these assemblies to stabilize NLRP3 monomers and dimers are essential for the conformational changes required for the assembly of the active inflammasome disc. Therefore, evaluation of NEK7-targeting modalities in the context of NLRP3 inflammasome formation, including small molecules that disrupt NEK7–NLRP3 PPIs, targeted protein degradation strategies, and RNAi-based approaches, requires assays in two broad categories: (1) assays that assess detect NEK7 engagement or disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction, and (2) assays that monitor downstream inflammasome activity (**Figure 8**). These assays can be further categorized as biochemical, biophysical, and cellular assays.

6.1 Biochemical Assays (NEK7–NLRP3 Interaction and Complex Assembly)

Several biochemical assays have been reported in the literature to evaluate NEK7–NLRP3 interactions, including co-immunoprecipitation (co-IP)⁵⁴, blue native PAGE (BN-PAGE)⁵⁵ for analysis of inflammasome complexes, and drug affinity responsive target stability (DARTS)⁵⁶. These methods have primarily been used to confirm inhibition of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPIs by specific compounds, rather than as high-throughput assays for screening compound libraries.

Co-immunoprecipitation (co-IP) can be used to evaluate PPIs. It involves lysing cells and using an antibody against one binding partner (NEK7 or NLRP3) to immunoprecipitate (IP) the protein complex, followed by western blot analysis to detect the interacting partner⁵⁴. A reduction in the co-IP signal in the presence of a NEK7-targeting compound indicates disruption of NEK7–NLRP3 binding. This method has been used as a central biochemical approach to identify rociletinib as an inhibitor of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI⁵⁷. In this study, co-IP experiments demonstrated that rociletinib treatment significantly reduced the association of endogenous NEK7 with NLRP3 following canonical inflammasome activation, indicating disruption of inflammasome assembly at the level of NEK7 recruitment. Importantly, rociletinib did not affect NLRP3 priming or the expression of inflammasome components, supporting a mechanism involving direct interference with complex formation rather than upstream signaling events. Additional co-IP experiments using epitope-tagged proteins (Flag-tagged NEK7 and VSV-tagged NLRP3) confirmed that rociletinib blocks NEK7–NLRP3 binding in reconstituted systems. In addition, co-IP has been used in a recent study to identify anemoside B4 as a small-molecule NEK7 binder that disrupts the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction⁵⁸. In this work,

co-IP experiments demonstrated reduced association of NEK7 with NLRP3 in both endogenous and reconstituted systems following compound treatment, consistent with impaired inflammasome assembly. These results further support the use of co-IP experiments to validate small-molecule disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI.

Blue Native PAGE (BN-PAGE) is a specialized gel electrophoresis technique that separates proteins under native (non-denaturing) conditions and can be used to resolve high-molecular-weight oligomers in cell extracts⁵⁵. The blue Coomassie dye, which binds proteins and imparts a negative charge so they migrate in the gel, also provides a visual loading control. A recent protocol described the use of BN-PAGE to visualize NEK7–NLRP3 complex formation in mouse macrophages⁵⁹. In this approach, mouse bone marrow-derived macrophages were primed with LPS and stimulated with ATP or nigericin to induce canonical NLRP3 inflammasome activation, after which native protein complexes were preserved using mild, non-denaturing lysis conditions and resolved by BN-PAGE. High-molecular-weight NLRP3–NEK7 complexes were subsequently detected by immunoblotting with NLRP3 or NEK7 antibodies. Importantly, this protocol was designed to monitor endogenous inflammasome assembly driven by physiological stimuli and does not involve treatment with small molecule NEK7–NLRP3 PPI inhibitors. Accordingly, BN-PAGE provides a qualitative biochemical readout of NEK7–NLRP3 complex formation and can be readily adapted to assess small-molecule disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI.

Drug affinity responsive target stability (DARTS) is a biochemical method used to identify direct small-molecule binding to a protein target based on ligand-induced protection from proteolytic degradation⁵⁶. In this approach, cell lysates or purified proteins are incubated with a test compound and subjected to limited proteolysis, with compound binding inferred from increased resistance of the target protein to protease digestion. DARTS was employed as a complementary biochemical strategy to co-immunoprecipitation in the identification of rociletinib as an NEK7–NLRP3 PPI inhibitor⁵⁷. In this study, rociletinib treatment selectively stabilized NEK7 against proteolytic degradation, consistent with direct binding to NEK7 rather than NLRP3. When combined with co-IP data demonstrating reduced NEK7–NLRP3 association upon rociletinib treatment, the DARTS results supported a mechanism in which rociletinib directly engages NEK7 and disrupts its recruitment to NLRP3 during inflammasome assembly. Similarly, in the study that identified anemoside B4 as a small-molecule NEK7 binder that disrupts the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction, DARTS was also used in combination with co-IP to demonstrate direct NEK7 engagement⁵⁸. Together, DARTS and co-IP provided orthogonal biochemical evidence linking direct NEK7 binding to functional inhibition of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction.

6.2 Biophysical Assays (Label-Free Binding and Interaction Evaluation)

In theory, all biophysical assays that characterize physical interactions between a ligand and a biomolecule can be employed to evaluate direct NEK7–ligand interactions. However, several biophysical techniques, including surface plasmon resonance (SPR), bio-layer interferometry (BLI), microscale thermophoresis (MST), and isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC), have been specifically reported to evaluate NEK7–small molecule binding interactions. A brief description of these methods is provided below.

Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) is a label-free optical technique used to measure binding interactions in real time, in which one binding partner is immobilized on a sensor chip and the potential binding partner is flowed over the surface⁶⁰. SPR can directly quantify the affinity and kinetics of the binding event. In the same study that described anemoside B4 as a small-molecule NEK7 binder that disrupts the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction⁵⁸, SPR was used, in addition to co-IP and DARTS, to directly measure binding between purified recombinant NEK7 and anemoside B4, yielding a dissociation constant (K_D) of approximately 4.37 μ M and providing quantitative evidence of direct NEK7–B4 binding.

Bio-layer interferometry (BLI) is a label-free binding assay similar in concept to SPR but using fiber-optic biosensors dipped into samples⁶¹. Although not typically sensitive enough to small molecules, BLI has been used in the literature to quantify the direct binding of cyclic peptide ligands to NEK7, as identified by phage display⁶². However, these studies focused on peptide–NEK7 interactions and did not directly evaluate NEK7–NLRP3 complex formation or its disruption.

Microscale thermophoresis (MST) is a technique that measures the movement of molecules in a temperature gradient, which changes upon binding, and typically one interaction partner is fluorescently labeled⁶³. In the case of rociletinib⁵⁷, described above, in which co-IP and DARTS were used, MST was also employed with purified NEK7 to quantify the dissociation constant between NEK7 and rociletinib ($K_D \approx 6.7 \mu$ M), confirming direct binding.

Isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) is the gold-standard method used to directly measure binding thermodynamics by detecting heat changes upon interaction, providing the K_D , binding stoichiometry, enthalpy change (ΔH), and entropy change (ΔS)⁶⁴. This technique, in addition to MST, was used to confirm the direct binding of rociletinib to NEK7⁵⁷, yielding a K_D value of approximately 3.7 μ M and corroborating the MST data.

6.3 Cellular Assays (Inflammasome Activation Endpoints)

Although cellular assays can also be used to assess cellular target engagement, as exemplified by anemoside B4⁵⁸, where a cellular thermal shift assay (CETSA) was employed to confirm NEK7 binding in a cellular context, they are more commonly applied to evaluate the functional inhibition of NEK7-licensed NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Importantly, these assays are applicable across a broad range of NEK7-targeting modalities, including small molecules that disrupt NEK7–NLRP3 PPIs, targeted protein degradation strategies, and RNAi-mediated knockdown to confirm the functional inhibition of NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Once NEK7 engagement by small molecules has been established using biochemical or biophysical approaches, or NEK7 suppression has been achieved through targeted protein degradation or RNAi-mediated knockdown, the next step is to determine whether this translates into the attenuation of downstream inflammasome signaling. Cell-based assays reported in the literature typically employ LPS-primed macrophages derived from either mouse sources (e.g., bone marrow-derived macrophages (BMDMs)) or human systems (e.g., THP-1 monocytes or primary human peripheral blood mononuclear cell (PBMC)-derived macrophages)⁶⁵. Following addition of a secondary activation stimulus (e.g., ATP or nigericin), these assays measure multiple downstream endpoints, including biochemical endpoints such as caspase-1 activation and gasdermin D cleavage, cytokine endpoints such as IL-1 β and

IL-18 production, and phenotypic endpoints such as cell death or pyroptosis and ASC speck formation, all of which are expected to be reduced upon effective NEK7 targeting (**Figure 8**). These endpoints also serve as functional biomarkers downstream of NEK7-mediated NLRP3 activation, and a brief description is provided below.

Caspase-1 activation: Upon inflammasome activation, pro-caspase-1 is processed into active caspase-1, leading to increased caspase-1 activity. This can be measured by western blotting, where either collected cell supernatants or cell lysates are probed for the p20 subunit of caspase-1 by immunoblotting. The appearance of the p20 fragment in the supernatant or cell lysate is indicative of inflammasome-driven caspase-1 activation. In the previously discussed example⁵⁷, the NEK7-targeting compound rociletinib significantly reduced nigericin-induced caspase-1 p20 levels in LPS-primed BMDMs, as detected by western blot analysis. In addition, homogeneous assays are available to measure caspase-1 enzymatic activity in a cellular context using commercially available kits, such as the Promega Caspase-Glo 1 Inflammasome Assay, which employs a pro-luminogenic caspase-1 substrate (WEHD-aminoluciferin)⁶⁶. Upon cleavage by active caspase-1, luciferase generates a glow-type luminescent signal proportional to caspase-1 activity. This assay is highly sensitive and can be performed directly in multiwell plates without additional cell-lysis steps beyond those included in the kit, making it suitable for 96-well screening. Another commonly used approach is the FLICA (Fluorescently Labeled Inhibitor of Caspases) assay⁶⁷. FLICA probes (e.g., FAM-YVAD-FMK for caspase-1) are cell-permeable and irreversibly bind active caspase-1 in live cells, labeling them with a fluorescent signal that can be quantified by flow cytometry or fluorescence microscopy.

Gasdermin D cleavage: Gasdermin D (GSDMD) is the executioner protein responsible for pyroptosis and is cleaved by caspase-1 into an approximately 30 kDa N-terminal fragment that forms membrane pores⁶⁸. This process can be monitored by western blot analysis, in which the loss of full-length GSDMD (~53 kDa) and the appearance of the N-terminal cleavage fragment in cell lysates are detected. Attenuation of GSDMD cleavage is correlated with reduced pyroptosis. Accordingly, effective NEK7-targeting modalities are expected to suppress GSDMD processing. In the case of rociletinib⁵⁷, western blot analysis revealed a marked reduction in GSDMD cleavage in nigericin-stimulated macrophages.

IL-1 β and IL-18 production: These two cytokines, the hallmarks of NLRP3 inflammasome activation, are most commonly quantified using ELISA⁶⁹, for which commercially available kits exist for cytokines of human and mouse origin. This is often performed in parallel with caspase-1 measurements to confirm that reduced IL-1 β levels are due to inflammasome inhibition rather than off-target effects. Modalities that target NEK7 and disrupt NEK7–NLRP3 interactions are therefore expected to attenuate IL-1 β and IL-18 production. For example, rociletinib showed dose-dependent inhibition of IL-1 β production, with an IC₅₀ value of 0.47 μ M as measured by ELISA⁵⁷.

Cell death/Pyroptosis: Inflammasome activation ultimately leads to a lytic form of cell death known as pyroptosis, which is mediated by the formation of GSDMD pores in the plasma membrane. Several assays are available to quantify pyroptosis, including lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release assays⁷⁰ and cell viability assays that utilize membrane-impermeable DNA-binding dyes. The LDH assay measures the activity of LDH released into the culture medium as cells undergo lysis during pyroptosis, using either colorimetric or luminescent substrates, and is available commercially, such as the Promega CytoTox or

Pierce LDH kits. The amount of LDH detected in the supernatant is proportional to the fraction of cells undergoing lytic cell death. In addition, membrane-impermeable DNA dyes, such as propidium iodide (PI)⁷¹ or 7-AAD⁷², are excluded by intact cells but readily penetrate and bind DNA in cells with compromised plasma membranes following NLRP3 activation, which occurs as a consequence of GSDMD pore formation and eventual membrane rupture. PI or 7-AAD-positive cells can be quantified by flow cytometry or monitored in real-time using time-lapse fluorescence imaging. These assays should be performed in parallel with cytokine release measurements to further validate inflammasome activation-mediated pyroptosis.

ASC speck formation: Upon NLRP3 inflammasome activation, ASC oligomerizes into a single macromolecular focus, known as an ASC speck which is a hallmark of canonical inflammasome assembly. ASC specks can be visualized by staining cells with an anti-ASC antibody, where activated cells display a single bright ASC punctum in the cytoplasm, whereas resting cells exhibit diffuse ASC localization⁷³. Inflammasome assembly can be quantified by measuring the percentage of cells containing ASC specks. In addition, cell lines that constitutively express GFP-tagged ASC are commercially available (InvivoGen THP-1 and A549 cells), eliminating the need for antibody-based staining to visualize ASC specks. Notably, the TREAT-AD Center has optimized a high-content imaging assay in a 384-well plate format using a commercially available THP-1 cell line that constitutively expresses GFP-tagged ASC (InvivoGen) to measure ASC speck formation; this assay is fully described in the NLRP3 M2 Target Enabling Package (TEP)⁷⁴. Furthermore, to enable higher-throughput quantification of ASC speck formation, imaging flow cytometry has been employed in the literature, combining features of fluorescence microscopy with flow cytometry.

6.4 Recommended Assay Strategy for Evaluating NEK7-Targeting Modalities

Based on the literature discussed above, evaluation of NEK7 targeting modalities should follow a stepwise strategy that first establishes direct engagement of NEK7 and disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction, followed by confirmation of functional inhibition of inflammasome assembly in cellular systems. Initial validation should therefore employ biochemical and biophysical assays such as co-IP, DARTS, BN PAGE, and label free binding techniques including SPR, MST, or ITC to demonstrate direct NEK7 binding and interference with the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. Once target engagement has been confirmed, cellular assays should be performed to determine whether this interaction translates into functional inhibition of NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Among the available cellular readouts, ASC speck formation assays are particularly informative because they directly quantify inflammasome assembly. Inhibition observed in ASC speck assays can be further supported by downstream biomarkers of inflammasome activity including reduced caspase-1 activation, decreased IL-1 β or IL-18 production, and attenuation of pyroptosis. Depending on assay accessibility and experimental resources, these methods may be applied individually. However, the use of multiple orthogonal assays in combination is generally preferred because this approach provides stronger mechanistic evidence for direct NEK7 engagement and inhibition of NEK7 licensed NLRP3 inflammasome activation, as illustrated by several literature examples discussed above.

7. THERAPEUTIC MODALITIES FOR TARGETING NEK7 IN NLRP3 INFLAMMASOME ACTIVATION

Based on the current mechanistic understanding of NEK7 involvement in NLRP3 activation, three main therapeutic modalities have been reported in the literature for targeting NEK7 to suppress inflammasome signaling (**Figure 8**): (1) RNAi-based post-transcriptional silencing strategies, such as siRNA or shRNA, which reduce NEK7 expression; (2) targeted protein degradation strategies, which reduce NEK7 protein levels; and (3) pharmacological disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI, which is a small molecule approach targeting the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction that is required to stabilize activation-competent NLRP3 monomers and dimers and to facilitate the NACHT domain conformational change necessary for assembly of the fully mature inflammasome complex. A detailed description of each modality is provided below.

7.1 RNAi Silencing of NEK7 using siRNA and shRNA

Two independent studies have provided detailed descriptions of RNA interference-based strategies for silencing NEK7 expression. These reports outlined the design and validation of both transient siRNA constructs⁷⁵ and lentivirus-mediated shRNA systems³⁰, demonstrating efficient reduction of NEK7 at the mRNA and protein levels. In addition to confirming knockdown efficiency, the study that utilized siRNA constructs systematically evaluated downstream functional consequences, including effects on cellular proliferation or NLRP3 inflammasome activation.

Figure 9. RNA interference strategies used to silence NEK7 expression in the literature. (A) Transient siRNA-mediated knockdown of NEK7. Two independent siRNA duplexes (NEK7-1 and NEK7-2) reported in the literature are shown with their sense and antisense sequences. These short interfering RNAs were designed to target distinct regions of the NEK7 mRNA and were chemically synthesized as duplexes for transient transfection, resulting in efficient reduction of NEK7 transcript and protein levels. **(B)** Lentiviral shRNA mediated silencing of NEK7. Two shRNA constructs, shNEK7-1 and shNEK7-2, reported in the literature are illustrated with their corresponding sense and antisense targeting sequences. The loop sequence and complete hairpin construct were not disclosed in the original report and are therefore depicted schematically as dashed loops. Targeted nucleotide positions within the human NEK7 transcript are indicated.

7.1.1 Transient siRNA-Mediated Silencing of NEK7

Chen *et al.* (2019) employed two naked synthetic siRNA duplexes (NEK7 siRNA1 and siRNA2) (**Figure 9A**) to transiently silence NEK7 in the mouse intestinal epithelial cell line MODE-K⁷⁵. Transfection efficiency

was confirmed by quantitative RT-PCR and immunoblotting, demonstrating robust suppression of NEK7 expression, with siRNA1 producing a more pronounced knockdown at both the mRNA and protein levels. Functionally, NEK7 silencing markedly attenuated LPS priming followed by ATP stimulation of NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Morphologically, typical pyroptotic features observed in control siRNA-transfected cells, including cell swelling, membrane pore formation, and vesicle-like pyroptotic bodies, were largely abolished following NEK7 knockdown. Consistent with this phenotype, ASC speck formation was significantly reduced, indicating impaired inflammasome assembly. At the biochemical level, NEK7 knockdown led to a substantial reduction in cleaved caspase-1 (p20), decreased GSDMD-N formation, and diminished NLRP3 protein levels. Importantly, IL-1 β release into the culture supernatant was significantly reduced following NEK7 silencing. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that siRNA-mediated depletion of NEK7 effectively suppresses NLRP3 inflammasome activation and downstream pyroptotic signaling *in vitro*. It is worth noting that these siRNA-mediated studies demonstrating suppression of NLRP3 inflammasome activation were conducted in the context of inflammatory bowel disease models; however, given the conserved role of the NEK7-NLRP3 interaction in inflammasome licensing, this mechanistic framework can be readily extended to neuroinflammatory conditions, such as AD.

7.1.2 Lentivirus-Mediated shRNA Silencing of NEK7

Zhou *et al.* (2016) utilized a lentivirus-mediated shRNA approach to achieve stable knockdown of NEK7 in hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) models³⁰. Only the sense and antisense targeting sequences are explicitly reported. Two independent shRNA constructs (shNek7-1 and shNek7-2) (**Figure 9B**), targeting nucleotides 328-350 and 718-740 of human NEK7 mRNA, respectively, were cloned into the pLKO.1 lentiviral vector and delivered into HepG2 and SMMC7721 cells. Quantitative RT-PCR and western blot analyses demonstrated that both constructs reduced NEK7 mRNA expression by up to approximately 80% and decreased NEK7 protein levels by up to approximately 90% relative to control shRNA (lenti-shNC). Functionally, NEK7 knockdown resulted in a significant reduction in HCC cell proliferation, as measured by CCK-8 viability assays, and suppressed tumor growth in a SMMC7721 xenograft mouse model. *In vivo*, tumors derived from NEK7-silenced cells were significantly smaller in both volume and weight compared with controls. Mechanistically, NEK7 depletion was associated with decreased cyclin B1 expression at both the mRNA and protein levels, whereas Bcl-2 and cyclin D1 were not significantly affected, suggesting that NEK7 promotes tumor cell proliferation primarily through regulation of cyclin B1. Importantly, this study did not evaluate NLRP3 inflammasome activation, IL-1 β maturation, caspase-1 activity, or pyroptosis. Thus, although shRNA-mediated NEK7 silencing achieved robust knockdown (80-90%) and translated into strong anti-proliferative and anti-tumorigenic effects in HCC models, it did not address whether this degree of NEK7 suppression leads to complete or partial inhibition of NLRP3 inflammasome signaling. Nevertheless, given the substantial and stable reduction of NEK7 expression achieved, these shRNA constructs could be readily used in studies evaluating the role of NEK7 in NLRP3 inflammasome signaling in the context of AD.

In addition to literature reported siRNA constructs, commercially available self-delivering RNA interference platforms, such as Accell siRNA (Horizon Discovery), provide an alternative approach for transient NEK7 silencing. Accell siRNAs are chemically modified to facilitate cellular uptake without the need for lipid-based transfection reagents and are designed for use in difficult to transfect cell types, including primary immune and neuronal cells. Pre-designed Accell siRNAs targeting both human and mouse NEK7 are

available, offering a convenient and reproducible option for mechanistic studies evaluating the functional role of NEK7 in NLRP3 inflammasome signaling.

7.2 Targeted Protein Degradation of NEK7 using Molecular Glues

Recent advances in targeted protein degradation have enabled the development of cereblon-recruiting molecular glues capable of selectively degrading NEK7. Through high-throughput screening and iterative structure-guided optimization, these studies identified small molecules that promote Cereblon (CRBN)-dependent ubiquitination and proteasomal degradation of NEK7 via engagement of its β -hairpin degron motif^{76, 77}. In addition to establishing potent and selective protein depletion, these reports further evaluated downstream functional outcomes, including modulation of NLRP3 inflammasome activation and cytokine release in relevant immune cell systems. A brief description of two recently discovered molecular glues, **NK7-902** and **LC-04-045**, is provided below.

NK7-902 emerged from a targeted CRBN molecular glue screening campaign designed to exploit the presence of a glycine-containing β -hairpin (g-loop) structural degron within NEK7 (residues 51-60), which closely resembles previously characterized CRBN-recruitable degrons⁷⁷. Screening of 2,545 CRBN-binding compounds using a NanoBiT-based recruitment assay identified NK7-288 as an initial hit capable of recruiting NEK7 to CRBN and inducing weak degradation in a high-throughput assay. Structure-guided optimization subsequently replaced the isoindolinone core of NK7-288 with a phthalimide moiety, yielding NK7-147, which displayed improved recruitment and degradation potency but achieved only partial degradation of endogenous NEK7 in THP1 cells at 1 μ M. Further elaboration of the solvent-exposed tail region ultimately led to NK7-902, a potent and selective CRBN molecular glue degrader capable of inducing complete degradation of endogenous NEK7 in cellular systems. Structural, mutational, and CRBN knockout studies confirmed that degradation is mediated through the recruitment of the NEK7 β -hairpin degron, with Gly57 being critical for ternary complex formation. In human primary monocytes, NK7-902 demonstrated highly efficient and concentration-dependent NEK7 degradation ($DC_{50} = 0.2$ nM, $D_{max} > 95\%$), achieving approximately 80% degradation within 1 h and sustained depletion thereafter. Proteomic profiling confirmed high selectivity, with NEK7 representing the most significantly downregulated protein. Functionally, NK7-902 inhibited NLRP3-dependent IL-1 β secretion *in vitro* in a donor and stimulus dependent manner, reaching up to $\sim 79\%$ inhibition under LPS+ATP stimulation, although inhibition was partial under certain activation conditions and in whole blood. In non-human primates, oral dosing produced profound and sustained NEK7 degradation; however, IL-1 β suppression was transient, highlighting a context and species dependent relationship between NEK7 depletion and NLRP3 inflammasome signaling. Although NK7-902 has demonstrated robust NEK7 degradation *in vitro* and in peripheral *in vivo* systems, including rodent and non-human primate models, no brain exposure or CNS penetration data have been disclosed to date. Thus, while NK7-902 represents the first structurally characterized and orally bioavailable CRBN molecular glue degrader of NEK7 and serves as a powerful probe for interrogating NEK7-dependent inflammasome biology, its utility in animal models of neurodegenerative disease will require further investigation to establish adequate CNS exposure.

LC-04-045 represents another highly selective and structurally characterized CRBN-recruiting molecular glue degrader of NEK7⁷⁶. The compound was identified through a NEK7 biased HiBiT (High-affinity BiT)

based high-throughput screening campaign of an in-house imide focused library, followed by iterative structure-activity relationship (SAR) optimization. Initial screening yielded LC-03-052 as a modest degrader ($DC_{50} = 26 \text{ nM}$, $D_{\text{max}} = 75\%$), and systematic modification of the biphenyl “tail” led to the discovery that ortho-chloro substitution significantly enhanced the degradation potency, resulting in LC-04-045 ($DC_{50} = 7 \text{ nM}$, $D_{\text{max}} = 90\%$ in MOLT-4 cells). Mechanistically, LC-04-045 promotes CRBN dependent ubiquitination and proteasomal degradation of NEK7, as confirmed by rescue with MLN4924, bortezomib, and pomalidomide, and by the inactivity of a CRBN-binding-deficient negative control analog. Proteome-wide mass spectrometry analysis demonstrated remarkable selectivity, with NEK7 identified as the only significantly downregulated protein. Degradation was strictly dependent on the G57-containing β -hairpin degron motif within NEK7, and mutagenesis studies further revealed that two adjacent residues (R35 and R50) were critical determinants of degrader selectivity. Functionally, LC-04-045 effectively suppressed IL-1 β and IL-18 release in LPS-stimulated human monocyte-derived macrophages, with IC_{50} values of 33.03 nM and 32.99 nM, respectively, comparable to the NLRP3 inhibitor MCC950. Overall, these findings position LC-04-045 as a highly potent tool compound for the mechanistic interrogation of NEK7-dependent inflammasome signaling. Similar to NK7-902, LC-04-045 has been primarily evaluated in cellular systems, and no data regarding brain exposure or central nervous system penetration have been reported to date. Therefore, its application in *in vivo* neurodegenerative disease models will require further studies to determine whether sufficient CNS exposure can be achieved.

7.3 Pharmacological Disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI

Another therapeutic strategy for modulating NEK7-dependent inflammasome activation involves pharmacological disruption of the PPI between NEK7 and NLRP3 using small molecules. Given that NEK7 functions primarily as a scaffolding factor to license NLRP3 inflammasome assembly, direct interference with the NEK7–NLRP3 interface represents a mechanistically distinct approach that does not necessarily require complete depletion of NEK7 protein. Several small-molecule PPI inhibitors capable of disrupting this interaction have been reported in the literature. Broadly, these compounds can be classified into two categories: those that inhibit the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction without exhibiting measurable NEK7 kinase inhibitory activity, and those that possess potent NEK7 kinase inhibition while simultaneously disrupting the NEK7–NLRP3 complex (**Figure 8**).

7.3.1 PPI Inhibitors Lacking NEK7 Kinase Inhibitory Activity

As shown in **Figure 10**, small molecules within this category can be broadly divided into two mechanistic classes: (1) direct NEK7-targeting ligands, including both covalent (e.g., rociletinib) and non-covalent (e.g., anemoside B4, entrectinib, licochalcone B, and berberine) binders that interfere with NEK7 engagement of NLRP3; and (2) interface-directed inhibitors designed to bind the LRR domain of NLRP3 (e.g., compound II-8 reported by Li et al.), thereby preventing NEK7 recruitment at its native docking surface. Importantly, as described previously, NEK7 kinase activity is essential for its canonical mitotic functions, including centrosome separation, spindle assembly, and regulation of microtubule organization during cell cycle progression. Consequently, global knockdown of NEK7, which also removes NEK7 catalytic activity from the cellular environment, could disrupt fundamental proliferative processes. The compounds in this category therefore represent a distinct class of chemical probes capable of selectively modulating the

scaffolding function of NEK7 in inflammasome licensing without perturbing its kinase activity, thereby enabling targeted suppression of NLRP3 activation while potentially preserving essential mitotic functions. Moreover, their development provides a compelling example of rigorous target validation, in which biophysical and biochemical methods such as DARTS, CETSA, SPR, ITC, mutagenesis, and co-IP are first employed to establish direct target engagement, followed by cellular assays to demonstrate that disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction translates into functional inhibition of inflammasome assembly, caspase-1 activation, and IL-1 β maturation.

Figure 10. Representative small-molecule inhibitors that disrupt the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction without inhibiting NEK7 catalytic activity. These compounds can be classified into two mechanistic categories: (1) direct NEK7-binding ligands, including covalent inhibitors such as rociletinib and noncovalent ligands such as anemoside B4, entrectinib, licochalcone B, and berberine, which bind NEK7 and interfere with its scaffolding interaction with NLRP3; and (2) interface-targeting inhibitors such as II-8, which bind the LRR domain of NLRP3 and prevent recruitment of NEK7 at its native docking surface. These compounds represent a distinct class of chemical probes that selectively disrupt the NEK7 scaffolding function required for inflammasome assembly while sparing its kinase catalytic activity, thereby enabling targeted suppression of NLRP3 inflammasome activation.

Rociletinib (ROC): A third-generation covalent EGFR inhibitor originally developed for mutant EGFR-positive non-small cell lung cancer was identified through kinase inhibitor library screening as a potent inhibitor of NLRP3 inflammasome activation⁵⁷. In LPS-primed bone marrow-derived macrophages, ROC inhibited monosodium urate (MSU) and ATP-induced IL-1 β release with submicromolar potency ($IC_{50} \approx 0.47 \mu\text{M}$ for MSU stimulation) and reduced caspase-1 cleavage, GSDMD processing, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release, and pyroptotic cell death without affecting IL-6 or TNF- α production, demonstrating specificity for the NLRP3 inflammasome. Mechanistically, rociletinib did not alter priming signals or upstream ionic fluxes but disrupted inflammasome assembly by blocking the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. As

discussed previously, DARTS assays demonstrated protection of NEK7 from proteolysis, and biophysical binding studies (MST and ITC) confirmed a direct interaction between ROC and purified NEK7. ROC covalently binds to Cys79 of NEK7 via its reactive α,β -unsaturated carbonyl moiety, and mutation of Cys79 abolished both binding and NLRP3 functional inhibition, establishing NEK7 as the direct molecular target. Consistent with this mechanism, *in vitro* kinase assays demonstrated that ROC did not inhibit NEK7 catalytic activity, indicating that its inflammasome inhibitory effect arises from disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI rather than kinase inhibition. Oral administration of rociletinib attenuated NLRP3-driven metainflammation in a high-fat diet-induced type 2 diabetes mouse model, reducing IL-1 β and IL-18 production and improving metabolic parameters. However, preclinical pharmacokinetic studies demonstrated that rociletinib exhibits negligible brain penetration, with brain-to-plasma C_{\max} ratios of approximately 0.08 in mice⁷⁸ and virtually no detectable uptake in monkey PET imaging studies⁷⁹. Accordingly, while rociletinib serves as a useful *in vitro* probe for mechanistic interrogation of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction, its minimal central nervous system (CNS) exposure limits its utility as an *in vivo* tool compound for neurodegenerative disease models, such as AD.

Anemoside B4: A pentacyclic triterpenoid saponin derived from *Pulsatilla chinensis*, was identified as a direct NEK7-binding small molecule that suppresses NLRP3 inflammasome activation⁵⁸. In LPS-primed macrophages stimulated with MSU, anemoside B4 inhibited NLRP3 inflammasome assembly, reduced ASC oligomerization, and attenuated caspase-1 activation, IL-1 β maturation, and GSDMD cleavage, thereby suppressing pyroptosis. Mechanistically, co-immunoprecipitation and fluorescence colocalization studies demonstrated that B4 disrupts the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. As discussed in the assay section, direct target engagement was confirmed by SPR, CETSA and DARTS assays, while molecular docking and site-directed mutagenesis identified key NEK7 residues (Ser46 and Phe168) critical for its binding. Anemoside B4 alleviated MSU-induced acute gouty arthritis in mice, reducing joint swelling, inflammatory cytokine production, and NLRP3 pathway activation, with NEK7 knockdown experiments supporting target specificity. Notably, independent tissue distribution studies in rats have reported detectable levels of anemoside B4 in the brain following oral administration of a herbal decoction containing the compound, indicating that anemoside B4 is capable of crossing the blood-brain barrier (BBB), albeit at relatively low concentrations compared to plasma exposure⁸⁰. Collectively, the available evidence supports anemoside B4 as a direct NEK7-binding small molecule that suppresses inflammasome activation via disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction and warrants further exploration of its potential as a molecular probe for NEK7-dependent neuroinflammatory signaling in AD.

Entrectinib: A clinically approved multi-kinase inhibitor targeting TRK, ROS1, and ALK, was identified through DARTS-based screening as a direct binder of NEK7 and a suppressor of NLRP3 inflammasome activation⁸¹. In LPS-primed mouse bone marrow-derived macrophages, entrectinib inhibited MSU and ATP-induced IL-1 β release with submicromolar potency ($IC_{50} \approx 0.88 \mu\text{M}$ for MSU stimulation and $\approx 0.73 \mu\text{M}$ for ATP stimulation) and reduced downstream markers of inflammasome activation. Mechanistic investigations demonstrated that entrectinib binds NEK7 at Arg121 and disrupts the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction, as confirmed by co-immunoprecipitation and mutagenesis studies. Importantly, *in vitro* kinase assays showed that entrectinib does not inhibit NEK7 catalytic activity, indicating that its inflammasome inhibitory effects arise from disrupting the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI rather than direct kinase inhibition. Preclinical pharmacokinetic studies in rats demonstrated that entrectinib achieves sustained brain and cerebrospinal

fluid exposure, with a CSF-to-unbound plasma ratio exceeding 0.2 at steady state, indicating meaningful CNS penetration⁸². In addition, clinical reports in patients with primary CNS malignancies have documented measurable entrectinib concentrations in the cerebrospinal fluid, supporting its ability to distribute across the BBB in humans⁸³. Overall, these findings demonstrate that entrectinib is a brain-penetrant small molecule capable of disrupting the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction and support its application as an *in vivo* probe of NEK7-dependent inflammasome signaling in AD.

Licochalcone B (LicoB): A bioactive chalcone isolated from licorice, was identified as a selective inhibitor of NLRP3 inflammasome activation⁸⁴. In LPS-primed BMDMs, LicoB dose-dependently inhibited nigericin- and ATP-induced caspase-1 activation, IL-1 β secretion, LDH release, and GSDMD cleavage, with an IC₅₀ of approximately 18.1 μ M for nigericin-induced IL-1 β production, without affecting NLRP3 or pro-IL-1 β expression levels. LicoB suppressed canonical and non-canonical NLRP3 activation across multiple stimuli in both mouse and human immune cells. Mechanistically, affinity pulldown experiments using LicoB-conjugated Sepharose beads demonstrated direct binding to NEK7, but not to NLRP3 or ASC, and co-immunoprecipitation assays confirmed that LicoB disrupted the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. Importantly, *in vitro* kinase assays showed that LicoB did not inhibit NEK7 catalytic activity, indicating that its anti-inflammasome effect arose from interference with the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI rather than kinase inhibition. LicoB exhibited protective effects in multiple NLRP3-driven inflammatory models, including LPS-induced septic shock, MSU-induced peritonitis, and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis. Although no direct measurements of CNS exposure for LicoB have been reported, several studies have shown that systemic administration of LicoB produces neuroprotective effects in a rat middle cerebral artery occlusion (MCAO) stroke model, improving neurological outcomes and reducing infarct size⁸⁵. These findings suggest biological activity in a CNS disease context, although definitive evidence of BBB penetration remains to be established. Taken together, these findings establish LicoB as a direct NEK7 binding small molecule that selectively inhibits NLRP3 inflammasome activation through disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction suggesting it could be used as a non-kinase inhibitory probe for studying NEK7 dependent inflammasome signaling in AD.

Berberine: A plant-derived isoquinoline alkaloid widely used in traditional Chinese medicine was identified using activity-based protein profiling (ABPP) as a direct proteomic target of NEK7⁸⁶. Chemical proteomic analysis demonstrated that berberine binds NEK7 through hydrogen bonding interactions involving the 2,3-methylenedioxy moiety and the Arg121 (R121) residue, a site located at the critical interface mediating NEK7–NLRP3 complex formation. Mutation of R121 abolished berberine binding, confirming target engagement specificity. Mechanistically, berberine selectively disrupted the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction without affecting upstream NF- κ B or TLR4 priming pathways, thereby suppressing NLRP3 inflammasome assembly. Specifically, in LPS-primed BMDMs, berberine was administered at micromolar concentrations (typically 10-20 μ M) prior to ATP or nigericin stimulation, resulting in marked suppression of mature IL-1 β secretion as measured by ELISA, reduced caspase-1 cleavage, and inhibition of ASC oligomerization in the Triton X-insoluble fraction, without affecting NF- κ B dependent priming signals. These findings indicate that berberine interferes with inflammasome assembly rather than transcriptional priming. *In vivo*, eight-week-old C57BL/6 mice were challenged with LPS to induce systemic inflammation, and berberine administration significantly reduced serum IL-1 β levels compared with vehicle-treated controls. Importantly, adenoviral-mediated NEK7 knockdown attenuated the anti-inflammatory effect of berberine,

demonstrating that its *in vivo* efficacy is NEK7-dependent and supporting target specificity. Taken together, the available evidence supports berberine as a direct NEK7-binding small molecule that suppresses NLRP3 inflammasome activation via disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. Importantly, quantitative brain distribution studies in rats have demonstrated measurable berberine concentrations in discrete brain regions, including the hippocampus and thalamus, following intravenous administration, with reported peak tissue levels in the low hundreds of ng/g range⁸⁷. Although berberine has been characterized as a P-glycoprotein substrate, which may limit extensive CNS accumulation, these data indicate that the compound is capable of crossing the BBB. Accordingly, berberine represents a naturally derived, brain-penetrant chemical scaffold that may serve as a tool for investigating NEK7-dependent neuroinflammatory signaling in AD.

II-8: In contrast to previously reported small molecules that directly target NEK7 to disrupt the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction, compound II-8 was rationally designed to bind the LRR domain of NLRP3, thereby preventing NEK7 engagement at its native PPI interface⁸⁸. Guided by structure-based virtual screening of a targetable pocket located at the NLRP3–NEK7 binding interface (PDB ID: 6NPY), iterative optimization of the pyridoimidazole scaffold led to the identification of II-8 as a second-generation inhibitor with enhanced potency and improved pharmacokinetic properties. In LPS-primed THP-M macrophages stimulated with ATP, II-8 inhibited IL-1 β release with an IC₅₀ of 3.33 \pm 1.05 μ M, representing an approximately 3-4 fold improvement over the first-generation analog. Mechanistic studies demonstrated that II-8 selectively suppresses NLRP3 inflammasome activation without affecting other inflammasomes, consistent with a target-specific mode of action. Molecular docking and 300-ns molecular dynamics simulations revealed stable engagement of the LRR domain, with hydrogen bonding to Arg697 and Asp745, as well as π – π stacking and electrostatic interactions involving His698 and Asp745. Biophysical assays confirmed direct binding to the LRR domain (ITC $K_D \approx 6 \mu$ M), with preferential affinity for LRR over NACHT or PYD domains as demonstrated by BLI analysis. Co-immunoprecipitation and fluorescence polarization assays further showed that II-8 effectively disrupts the NLRP3–NEK7 interaction. In an adjuvant-induced arthritis (AIA) rat model, II-8 exhibited improved pharmacokinetic behavior, including an extended elimination half-life (\sim 236 min, oral), and demonstrated significant *in vivo* anti-inflammatory efficacy. However, no central nervous system exposure or brain distribution data have been reported to date. Therefore, although II-8 represents a first-in-class small molecule that inhibits NLRP3 inflammasome activation by directly targeting the LRR structural domain of NLRP3 and blocking NEK7 recruitment, its application as an *in vivo* tool compound in the context of AD will require further evaluation to establish adequate brain exposure and CNS pharmacokinetics.

Figure 11. SAR highlighting the requirement of a urea linker for inhibition of NLRP3 inflammasome activation by potent NEK7 kinase inhibitors. Representative chemotypes disclosed by Halia Therapeutics illustrate that type II inhibitors containing a central urea functionality (series **1a-1c**) exhibit potent NEK7 kinase inhibition and robust suppression of IL-1 β production, consistent with disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. In contrast, structurally related tertiary amide analogs (type $1_{1/2}$ like inhibitors) retain strong NEK7 kinase inhibitory activity but fail to inhibit IL-1 β production, indicating that catalytic inhibition alone is insufficient to block inflammasome activation. These findings support a mechanism in which urea-containing inhibitors stabilize an inactive NEK7 conformation compatible with disruption of its scaffolding interaction with NLRP3, thereby linking kinase conformational state to inflammasome regulatory function.

7.3.2 PPI Inhibitors with Strong NEK7 Kinase Inhibitory Activity

A particularly interesting class of NEK7 directed inflammasome inhibitors was initially disclosed by Halia Therapeutics in a series of patent applications, most notably US20230210853A1⁸⁹, which outlines both a mechanistic hypothesis and several structurally distinct chemotypes unified by a shared pharmacophore. Within this disclosure, multiple compounds bearing a central urea functionality were reported to exhibit potent inhibition of NEK7 kinase activity and robust suppression of IL-1 β production in cellular inflammasome assays. A striking SAR emerged from these studies, in which replacing the urea linker with a corresponding tertiary amide preserved potent NEK7 kinase inhibition but completely abolished IL-1 β production inhibition (**Figure 11**). The urea functionality is a key structural feature of type II kinase inhibitor architecture, and the urea-containing compounds described in the application are consistent with this class of inhibitors. The inventors proposed that these analogs stabilize the inactive DLG-out conformation of NEK7, which could alter the structural elements required for NEK7 engagement with NLRP3, thereby disrupting the NEK7–NLRP3 PPI. In contrast, the tertiary amide analogs, although retaining catalytic inhibition of NEK7, may not promote the same inactive conformational state and therefore fail to induce the structural changes necessary to impair inflammasome assembly. The application further organizes these molecules into several structurally distinct series, designated **1a-1e**, which retain the urea pharmacophore while exploring variations in hinge-binding motifs, aryl substitutions, and solvent-exposed substituents. A detailed discussion of the chemical architecture and SAR trends within selected series is provided below.

Figure 12. Representative structures and SAR of Series Ia aminopyrazolopyrimidine-based NEK7 inhibitors. Series Ia compounds are built on an aminopyrazolopyrimidine hinge-binding scaffold linked through a central urea functionality to substituted heteroaryl tail groups consistent with a type II kinase inhibitor pharmacophore. Representative analogs (**1-9**; designations Ia-12, Ia-13, Ia-14, Ia-21, Ia-25, Ia-30, Ia-32, Ia-45, and Ia-33) illustrate key structural variations within the series. Color-coded indicators denote reported inhibitory potency against NEK7 kinase activity and suppression of IL-1 β production in cellular inflammasome assays. Across the series, compounds exhibiting low-nanomolar NEK7 IC_{50} values consistently demonstrate potent inhibition of IL-1 β release, whereas reduced kinase inhibitor potency is associated with diminished cellular activity, supporting a mechanistic link between NEK7 inhibition and suppression of NLRP3 inflammasome activation. Compound **5** (Ia-25; Ofirnoflast), highlighted as the clinical development candidate, exemplifies this relationship and has advanced into clinical evaluation as a first-in-class NEK7-targeting inflammasome inhibitor.

Series Ia: Series Ia was built around an aminopyrazolopyrimidine hinge-binding core connected through a central urea linker to a substituted heteroaryl tail, consistent with a type II kinase inhibitor architecture. A notable observation within Series Ia is the visual correlation between NEK7 kinase inhibitory potency and the suppression of IL-1 β production in cellular inflammasome assays. As summarized in **Figure 12**, compounds exhibiting low-nanomolar NEK7 IC_{50} values consistently demonstrated potent inhibition of IL-1 β release, whereas attenuation of kinase potency was accompanied by reduced cellular activity. This visual correlation supports the mechanistic hypothesis proposed in the application that NEK7 kinase inhibition underlies the observed suppression of NLRP3 inflammasome activation in this chemotype.

Among these analogs, compound **5** (Ia-25) emerged as a preclinical candidate and has advanced into clinical evaluation under the name Ofirnoflast. In a subsequent publication, Ofirnoflast is described as a first-in-class, orally bioavailable NEK7 inhibitor that suppresses NLRP3 inflammasome activation by targeting the scaffolding function of NEK7 rather than directly inhibiting NLRP3 itself⁹⁰. In a radiometric kinase assay (Hotspot), Ofirnoflast inhibited NEK7 enzymatic activity with an IC_{50} of 46 nM, consistent with engagement at or near the ATP-binding site. In cellular models, including PMA-differentiated THP-1 macrophages and human iPSC-derived microglia, Ofirnoflast dose-dependently inhibited ASC speck

formation, IL-1 β release, and pyroptotic cell death following LPS priming and nigericin or ATP stimulation. Mechanistically, the authors proposed that Ofirnoflast engages an allosteric pocket adjacent to the ATP-binding site of NEK7 and induces a stabilized conformational state incompatible with inflammasome assembly. Differential scanning fluorimetry demonstrated significant thermal stabilization of NEK7 upon compound binding, whereas limited proteolysis assays revealed altered protease susceptibility consistent with a compound-induced conformational shift. Molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations further suggested a type II kinase inhibitor binding mode involving displacement of the DLG motif into an “out” conformation, thereby exposing an adjacent allosteric pocket and stabilizing a non-canonical NEK7 conformation. The authors concluded that this conformational locking mechanism disrupts NEK7–NLRP3 PPI, effectively blocking inflammasome assembly. *In vivo*, Ofirnoflast achieved oral bioavailability with plasma exposures exceeding its cellular EC₅₀ values and demonstrated significant suppression of IL-1 β , IL-18, and broader inflammatory cytokines in a DSS-induced colitis model. The compound has progressed into Phase 2 clinical trials, representing one of the first NEK7-targeting small-molecule kinase inhibitors to enter human evaluation for inflammasome-driven inflammatory diseases.

Figure 13. Representative structures and SAR of Series Ib pyrrolopyridine-based NEK7 inhibitors. Series Ib compounds incorporate a pyrrolopyridine hinge-binding core connected via an ether linkage to a central urea pharmacophore. Representative analogs (**1-5**; designations Ib-4, Ib-12, Ib-18, Ib-5, and Ib-8) illustrate structural diversity within this scaffold. Color-coded indicators denote inhibitory potency against NEK7 kinase activity and suppression of IL-1 β production in cellular inflammasome assays. In contrast to Series Ia, Series Ib compounds exhibit only moderate to weak NEK7 kinase inhibition while retaining potent suppression of IL-1 β release, indicating a lack of direct correlation between enzymatic potency and cellular inflammasome inhibition for this chemotype.

Series Ib: Series Ib is structurally distinguished from Series Ia by the incorporation of a pyrrolopyridine hinge-binding head group connected through an ether linkage to the central urea pharmacophore. While

these compounds retain the urea motif characteristic of type II kinase inhibitor architecture, modification of the hinge-binding core results in a distinct pharmacological profile. In contrast to Series Ia, compounds within Series Ib exhibit only moderate to weak NEK7 kinase inhibitory activity, with IC_{50} values generally shifting into the mid- to high-nanomolar or micromolar range. Despite this attenuation in enzymatic potency, all evaluated members of this series maintain robust suppression of IL-1 β production in cellular inflammasome assays. As summarized in **Figure 13**, no clear visual correlation is observed between NEK7 catalytic inhibition and IL-1 β inhibition within this scaffold. Compounds with relatively weak NEK7 enzymatic potency retain potent cellular IL-1 β production inhibition activity, and reductions in kinase inhibition do not proportionally translate into diminished inflammasome suppression. This divergence from the trend observed in Series Ia suggests that, for Series Ib, suppression of IL-1 β production may not be strictly dependent on the magnitude of catalytic inhibition measured in isolated kinase assays. Instead, these data raise the possibility that alternative mechanisms may contribute to inflammasome inhibition.

Series Ic: Series Ic retains the central urea pharmacophore characteristic of the type II kinase inhibitor architecture but incorporates a pyrrolopyridine hinge-binding head group linked through an ether spacer to the distal aryl system. Similar to Series Ia, a clear visual correlation is observed between NEK7 kinase inhibitory potency and suppression of IL-1 β production in cellular inflammasome assays. As illustrated in **Figure 14**, compounds displaying stronger NEK7 IC₅₀ values consistently demonstrate enhanced inhibition of IL-1 β release, whereas attenuation of kinase potency is accompanied by diminished cellular activity. This parallel trend between biochemical kinase inhibition and functional inflammasome suppression within Series Ic reinforces the mechanistic hypothesis advanced in the patent disclosure that stabilization of the inactive DLG-out conformation of NEK7 underlies disruption of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction. In addition to the urea-containing analogs, the application describes a series of compounds (Halia series II-1–II-18) in which the central urea linker was replaced with a tertiary amide functionality that retained potent NEK7 kinase inhibitory activity. Notably, these amide analogs exhibited markedly diminished or abolished inhibition of IL-1 β production, highlighting the critical role of urea functionality in mediating inflammasome suppression.

Overall, across the urea-containing chemotypes, compounds within Series Ia and Ic display a clear correlation between NEK7 kinase inhibition and IL-1 β production inhibition, whereas Series Ib reveals mechanistic complexity, as potent suppression of IL-1 β production is observed despite only moderate to weak NEK7 catalytic IC₅₀ values. Importantly, urea functionality is also a defining feature of established NLRP3 NACHT-domain binders, such as MCC950 and its derivatives. Given the absence of direct biochemical or structural evidence demonstrating that these type II NEK7 inhibitors disrupt the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction through conformational modulation of NEK7, an alternative mechanistic hypothesis warrants consideration. It is plausible that urea-containing compounds within this series may directly engage the NLRP3 NACHT domain, analogous to MCC950, thereby stabilizing an inactive NLRP3 conformation and preventing the conformational transitions required for inflammasome assembly. Collectively, these observations highlight the need for integrated biochemical, biophysical, and structural studies to definitively establish the molecular target and mechanism of action of this emerging class of urea-containing inflammasome inhibitors with NEK7 kinase inhibitory activity.

7.4 Recommended Modalities for Evaluating NEK7 as a Therapeutic Target in AD

Selection of NEK7-targeting modalities should be guided by both mechanistic specificity and the likelihood of achieving meaningful exposure in relevant experimental systems. For *in vitro* studies focused on the scaffolding role of NEK7 in NLRP3 inflammasome licensing, the most informative modalities are small molecules that directly disrupt the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction without inhibiting NEK7 kinase catalytic activity. Compounds such as rociletinib, anemoside B4, entrectinib, LicoB, and berberine are therefore particularly valuable as mechanistic tool compounds in AD-relevant cellular models, including microglia, macrophages, and iPSC-derived neuroimmune models, because they enable evaluation of NEK7-dependent inflammasome signaling while potentially preserving the canonical mitotic and microtubule-regulatory functions of NEK7. This distinction may be important because NEK7 kinase activity is required for fundamental cellular processes, including centrosome organization, spindle assembly, and cell cycle

progression, and global disruption of these functions could confound interpretation of inflammasome-related phenotypes.

For *in vivo* studies in AD mouse models, modality selection should place greater emphasis on reported or plausible brain exposure. Among the currently described small-molecule NEK7 binders that disrupt the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction, entrectinib appears to be the strongest available *in vivo* tool compound because meaningful CNS penetration has been reported in both preclinical and clinical settings. Berberine and anemoside B4 may also warrant consideration as exploratory *in vivo* probes, as available studies suggest measurable brain exposure, although the extent of CNS penetration appears more limited and may be insufficient for robust target modulation without careful pharmacokinetic confirmation. In contrast, rociletinib is unlikely to be suitable for *in vivo* AD studies because its negligible brain penetration limits its utility in neurodegenerative disease models, despite its clear value as an *in vitro* mechanistic probe. Similarly, the currently disclosed NEK7 molecular glue degraders, including NK7-902 and LC-04-045, are highly attractive for mechanistic studies in peripheral or cellular models, but their use in AD animal models remains premature because no CNS exposure data have yet been reported. These degraders should therefore presently be viewed primarily as powerful *in vitro* tools for defining the effect of NEK7 depletion rather than as validated *in vivo* probes.

RNAi approaches such as siRNA and shRNA remain highly useful for mechanistic validation *in vitro*, particularly in AD-relevant cellular systems where direct confirmation of NEK7 dependence is needed. However, the approaches reported to date are less immediately translatable to *in vivo* pharmacological studies and therefore require advanced design and delivery approaches amenable to CNS exposure.

Overall, for AD focused studies, the most attractive near-term strategy is to prioritize direct modulators of the NEK7–NLRP3 interaction that preserve NEK7 kinase activity, use these compounds together with RNAi methods for *in vitro* target validation, and advance modalities with demonstrated or experimentally confirmed brain exposure into AD mouse models. This framework should enable clearer separation of the inflammasome-licensing function of NEK7 from its essential cell cycle roles while prioritizing the modalities most likely to provide interpretable pharmacology in neurodegenerative disease settings.

8. CONCLUSION

NEK7 has emerged as a critical regulator of NLRP3-inflammasome activation and represents a targetable node linking cellular stress signals to innate immune activation. Current evidence implicates dysregulated NLRP3 inflammasome signaling in multiple aspects of AD pathology from amyloid- β and tau-induced microglial activation to chronic neuroinflammation that accelerates synaptic loss. This convergence suggests NEK7 is a potential therapeutic target with its kinase-independent scaffolding role in NLRP3 assembly offering selectivity advantages over broader NLRP3-inflammasome inhibition and may enable modulation of neuroinflammation with improved tolerability compared to systemic NF- κ B or cytokine pathway blockade. Here we have synthesized the current literature around NEK7 and described targeting strategies from the structural determinants of NEK7–NLRP3 binding and kinase domain function to the cellular assays available for interrogating inflammasome engagement in primary microglia and brain tissue. We systematically reviewed emerging therapeutic modalities including RNAi-based silencing, targeted protein degradation, and small-molecule inhibitors designed to disrupt the NEK7–NLRP3 interface.

Critically, we outlined evidence-based recommendations for experimental design, target engagement readouts, and assay selection to advance preclinical validation and clinical translation of NEK7-directed therapeutics. This practical framework for drug discovery efforts will support the development of selective, brain-penetrant NEK7 inhibitors as disease-modifying approaches for AD and related dementia driven by NLRP3-dependent neuroinflammation.

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